

KALPI IN THE 15TH CENTURY

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THE 15th century is a period of great cultural significance in the history of North India but little work has been done on it. Many aspects of the Indo-Muslim culture during the 'subsequent centuries, particularly the background of the rise of religious trends, both revivalist and syncretic, would remain obscure unless a detailed and indepth study is made of life and culture in the 15th century. No doubt, the Delhi Sultanate disintegrated towards the close of the 14th century, giving rise to centrifugal tendencies, the legacy of its cultural and political system remained. Soon, certain *muqṭa's* and *zamīndārs* managed to seize neighbouring territories, established peace and order there and thus carved out independent kingdoms and principalities for themselves. The hagiographic literature and the chronicles, produced in these kingdoms, not only provide interesting information about the proliferation of the Muslim culture, developed in Delhi, but also shed considerable light on the activities of the Sufi saints and 'Ulamā' (religious divines) who had migrated from Delhi to different cities on the eve of Timūr's invasion in A.D. 1398. We also get from these insights into social life in the new urban centres founded by the regional sultans.

The kingdoms and principalities being smaller in area were more manageable and the respective rulers took keen interest in the development of different areas under their rule. In an attempt to augment their resources and surpass the neighbouring rulers in power and grandeur of their courts, these rulers tended to create conditions conducive to peace and prosperity in their territories. The rise of principalities and regional kingdoms is thus marked both by the growth of population and by urbanization. New cities and towns were founded and adorned with beautiful buildings, *madrasahs*, mosques, palaces and gardens. Some of these newly founded cities not only succeeded

in rapidly developing the economic functions of a true city but also came up to Baranī's definition of *miṣr-i jāmi'*¹ (the perfect city). Their rise helped the growth of Muslim population on the one hand and the spread of Islam on the other. The case of Kalpi illustrates this point.

It should also be pointed out that most of the founders of regional kingdoms and principalities represented the culture and traditions of the Delhi court, which had been the resort of 'Ulamā', *Mashā'ikh* (Sufi saints), artists and men of culture for two centuries. The courts organized by them were a replica of the Delhi sultan's court. Moreover, they patterned their administrative system on the model of the Delhi Sultanate. In the beginning, scholars, poets, artists and craftsmen, who contributed to the growth and glory of their cities, generally came from Delhi, and through them the Delhi culture permeated far and wide. Afterwards, the generous patronage extended by the rulers to men of learning, religion and arts attracted foreign emigrants to their cities. They came from different Muslim countries and were able to make their own contribution to the Indo-Muslim culture of Northern India.

The important kingdoms and principalities that emerged after the break up of the Delhi Sultanate were kingdoms of Jaunpur, Malwa and Gujarat, and the principalities of Khandesh, Jalore, Nagaur, Gwalior, Bayana, Chanderi and Kalpi. The towns and cities which the regional rulers chose or founded as their military and administrative headquarters developed into centres of Islamic culture, and played an important role in sustaining not only the Islamic institutions and the traditional Indian arts and crafts but also the arts and crafts that had developed in Delhi under the influence of foreign immigrants during

(1) According to Ḍiyā' al-Dīn Baranī, a city that contained, in addition to its vast population and bazars, a large number of scholars, scientists, artists, traders, craftsmen and artisans skilled in their respective professions and crafts deserved to be called *miṣr-i jāmi'*. In his days Delhi had acquired the status of a perfect city. He glows with pride when he refers to Delhi's scholars, scientists, craftsmen, etc. who had gained world wide fame for their mastery over different sciences, crafts, etc. (*Ta'rikh-i Firuz Shāhi*, ed. Sir Sayyid Aḥmad Khān [Calcutta, 1862], pp. 352, 353, 355, 469, 474.)

the 13th and 14th centuries. The references contained in miscellaneous contemporary sources to the immigrants from Delhi and the area around it, seeking asylum in places of safety, help us analyze the demographic, social and economic processes.

This paper attempts first to describe the transformation of Kalpi into a centre of Islamic learning and culture, its population and social structure, and then to discuss the cultural and political influence that it exercised on the satellite towns and villages included in the principality. Further, the problem of social relations that the rulers of Kalpi faced, and the efforts made by the members of the military and religious elite to bring about co-existence of different communities and social groups in society have been analyzed. Incidentally, notice has been taken of political developments that affected the socio-economic life in the area under study.

The City of Kalpi:

Kalpi, though reduced to the size of a small and unimportant village in the 14th century,² was a place of great antiquity. Till the close of the 14th century it formed part of the nuclear region of classical Hindu culture which Islamic institutions and Muslim culture had not been able to penetrate. It, however, underwent socio-economic change and began to grow into a city when Malikzādah Maḥmūd, son of *Majlis-i 'Alī*³ *A'zam Humāyūn* Firūz Khān Turk⁴ (the *Wazīr-i Mumālik*

(2) Kalpi is the headquarters of a *taḥṣīl* of the same name in the district of Jalaun, Uttar Pradesh site 26° 8' N, 79° 45' E on the Jamuna river, 22 miles away from the district headquarters.

(3) *Majlis-i 'Alī* and *Masnad-i 'Alī* (exalted lordship) were the honorific titles used as prefix to the names or main titles of the high grandees during the Sultanate period. For instance, the vizir in the 13th and 14th centuries was addressed as *Majlis-i 'Alī*. Majd al-Dīn Abū al-Ma'ālī Mu'ayyid bin Muḥammad Jarjāmji, who translated Ghazālī's *Iḥyā' 'Ulūm al-Dīn* in Persian in 1220-21 at the instance of Nizām al-Mulk Junaydī, calls his patron as *Majlis-i 'Alī* Nizām al-Mulk. The *Inshā'-i Māhrū* also contains Sultan Firūz Shāh's (1351-1382) *farmān*, relating to the appointment of *Khān-i Jahān* Maqbāl as vizir. In this *farmān*, *Khān-i Jahān* Maqbāl has been mentioned with all his titles including those of *Majlis-i 'Alī* and *A'zam Humāyūn*

under Sultan Tughluq Shāh [A.D. 1388-1389]), who had been driven away by Rā'i Šābir of Etawah and Rā'i Adhran of Bhogaon⁵ from the *shiqq* of Firuzpur,⁶ made it the headquarters of his army in A.D. 1390.⁷ Shortly afterwards he was joined by many other nobles who also had been forced to vacate their forts and *iqṭā's*, such as Tughluqpur (former Akhal), Phapoond, Chandwar, Shamsabad, Patiali, etc. because of the threat posed by the Chauhan chiefs of the region.⁸ All of them came to Kalpi with their followers with the result that it rapidly developed into a city of great importance. Being resourceful, they built beautiful

(Jarjāmji's Persian translation, MS., British Museum, London, Or. 8194, f. 3a; 'Ayn al-Mulk 'Abd Allāh bin Māhrū, *Inshā'-i Māhrū*, ed. Shaikh Abdur Rashid [Lahore, 1965], letter no. 2, p. 9; Muḥammad Bihāmad Khānī, *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi*, MS., British Museum, London, Or. 137, ff. 419b, 430a, 442a-b). Similarly, *Masnad-i 'Alī* and *Majlis-i 'Alī* have also been used with titles of high nobles in the official histories of Malwa ('Alī bin Maḥmūd al-Kirmānī, known as Shihāb Ḥakim, *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī*, MS., British Museum, London, Or. 11, 140, f. 38b; Anonymous, *Ta'rikh-i Nāṣir Shāhī*, MS. British Museum, London, Or. 1803, f. 14a). Ḥājji Dabīr gives clue to their connotation. Explaining these titles he states that it was the custom in his country to entitle the King's deputy (*Nā'ib-i Muṭlaq*) as *Masnad-i 'Alī* and the vizir as *Majlis-i 'Alī*. (*Zafar al-Wāliḥ* (ed.) [London, 1921], vol. ii, p. 613.)

(4) Both Muḥammad Bihāmad Khān and Yaḥyā Sirhindī regard the founder of Kalpi dynasty as of Turkish origin. Contrary to them, Shihāb Ḥakim calls Maḥmūd "Mughal" not Turk. Since the Mughals were looked down upon after Timūr's invasion, the rulers of Kalpi must have liked to call themselves "Turk" instead of "Mughal." (Yaḥyā b. Aḥmad Sirhindī, *Ta'rikh-i Mubārak Shāhī*, ed. M. Hidayat Husain [Calcutta, 1931], p. 134; *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī*, abridged and ed. Nurul Hasan Ansari [Delhi, 1968], p. 59.)

(5) It is the headquarters of a *taḥṣīl* in the district of Mainpuri, sit. 27° 16' N, 79° 11' E.

(6) Its former name was Kanar. Sultan Firūz Shāh built a fort and having named it Firuzpur, made it the headquarters of the *shiqq* of the same name (*Shiqq-i Firūzpur*). It is now a deserted place, about two miles off Jagmanpur. Sit. 26° 25' N, 79° 16' E and is still known as Kanar Khera. (Cf. *District Gazetteer*, Jalaun [1921], vol. xxv, 170.)

(7) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi*, f. 419b.

(8) *Ibid.*, ff. 418b-419a-b.

houses for their residence with mosques and *madrasahs* adjacent to them. Gardens were also laid down all around the city. The *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, though very brief, sheds some light on the rapid expansion of Kalpi into a city. According to it, A'zam Humāyūn Maḥmūd Khān bin Firūz Khān Turk, whom Sultan Muḥammad Shāh II (son of Firūz Khān) had honoured with the title of *Khān* and the grant of the *iqṭā'* of Mahoba in addition to the *iqṭā'* of Kalpi in 139,3⁹ took pains to develop his seat of government as a centre of culture. He demarcated a fairly large area, encircled it with strong and lofty walls and then diverted much of his resources towards the building of a massive palace-fortress.¹⁰ A number of mosques and other buildings of public utility were erected. On the completion of the *ḥiṣār*¹¹ (fortification), he named his city Muhammadabad after the Prophet of Islam. Along with the city, the suburb of Kalpi was also developed.¹² Maḥmūd Khān welcomed all those scholars, *Sayyids*, artisans, etc. who fled from Delhi and other disturbed areas to escape from Timūr's army and sought asylum in Muhammadabad in 1398. As a result of this influx, Muhammadabad became *Shahr-i Mu'azzam* (great city) and became famous as Muhammadabad alias Kalpi.¹³

In fact, the exodus of people caused by Timūr's invasion of Delhi considerably added to the population of towns in the Sharqī dominions, Kalpi principality and the Malwa region. The refugees went as far as Gujarat. The contemporary writers of Gujarat and Kalpi refer only to refugees belonging to the class of *Akābir*, *Ashrāf* and *Umarā'-i Nāmdār*, i.e. the members of the religious/military elite,¹⁴ but, as Sharaf al-Dīn Yazdī tells us, often the entire population evacuated town or

(9) *Ibid.*, ff. 429b-430a; Yahyā Sirhindī says that the combined *iqṭā's* were called as *Shiqq-i Kalpi wa-Mahoba*. (*Ta'rikh-i Mubārak Shāhī*, p. 168.)

(10) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 419b, 439a-b, 437a.

(11) *Ibid.*, f. 419b, 450a-451a, for the description of *ḥiṣār* (fortification).

(12) *Ibid.*, f. 438b.

(13) *Ibid.*, f. 443a.

(14) Anonymous, *Ta'rikh-i Gujarāt*, MS., Br. Museum, London, Or. 1819, f. 27b; *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 442b.

cities on the approach of Timūr's army.¹⁵ We may, however, assume that the greater part of the caravans of refugees consisted of noblemen, traders, craftsmen and workers. The evidence available in Sufi literature shows that the larger portion of Delhi's population had already left for safety before Timūr reached the vicinity of Delhi.¹⁶

The cities of Jaunpur, Mandu and Kalpi, being comparatively close to Delhi, received the largest number of immigrants. With their arrival, Kalpi began to develop as a centre of Muslim culture and Islamic learning and started humming with economic activity. This influx considerably enhanced the military strength of Kalpi's ruler who seized territories from the neighbouring Muslim *muḥta's* and Rajput *zamīndārs* and declared his independence. He assumed the title of Sultan Nāṣir al-Dīn Maḥmūd Shāh.¹⁷ With his declaration of independence, Kalpi, his capital, was addressed as *Ḥaḍrat-i Muḥammadābād*.¹⁸

We may now briefly analyze the odd bits of information that enables us, at least to some extent, to form an idea about the size of the population of Kalpi in the 15th century. Authentic information about the size of the city's population is lacking. We may, however, apply the method suggested by Diyā' al-Dīn Baranī in his *Ta'rikh-i Firūz Shāhī* to arrive at a rough estimate. Baranī has quoted Sultan Balban

(15) *Zafarnāmah*, ed. Muḥammad Allāhdād (Calcutta, 1888), vol. ii, pp. 77-78.

(16) Maḥmūd Ṣāfi Irijī, *Tuḥfat al-Majālis*, the *malfūzāt* of a 15th-century saint, Shaykh Aḥmad Maghribī, quoted by K. A. Nizami. *Medieval India—A Miscellany* (Aligarh, 1975), vol. 3, p. 246.

(17) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 436a.

(18) *Ibid.*, ff. 439a-b, 442b. It is wrongly held by modern scholars that Delhi was called *Ḥaḍrat-i Dihlī* on account of the tombs of many leading Sufi saints there. In fact, the permanent headquarters of a sultan was known as *Ḥaḍrat*. For instance, Delhi came to be known as *Ḥaḍrat-i Dihlī* in 1210 when Iltutmish made it the capital of his sultanate, much before any famous Sufi saint was buried there. The writers who compiled works on different subjects under the patronage of Nizām al-Mulk Junaydī refer to Delhi as *Ḥaḍrat-i Dihlī*. (Cf. Persian translation of *Iḥyā' 'Ulūm al-Dīn*, f. 3b; *Kitāb al-Ṣaydnah*, ed. M. Sotudeh and I. Afshar, Iran [1352 Shamsi], p. 13.)

Muḥammad Bihāmad Khān refers to Mandu also as *Ḥaḍrat-i Shādī' ābād*. (*Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 428a.)

as having said that army generals commanding twelve thousand *sawārs* were required for the effective control of a newly-conquered vilayet. Considering the families and dependants of the *sawārs* and the officers, such as *kārkuns* (account clerks), domestic servants and footmen, the total number would be around one hundred thousand persons. Baranī approves of the figure.¹⁹ If we accept it the average number of dependants of one military man comes to more than eight persons. We should exclude the footmen from this class of people, as there is no evidence of their actual strength in Kalpi, and reduce the number of dependants for each *sawār* to four in order to be more reasonable in working out a tentative figure.

We are informed by Shihāb al-Dīn al-'Umarī that a *Khān* commanded in India ten thousand *sawārs*,²⁰ a *Malik* one thousand, and an *Amīr* one hundred. Al-'Umarī's statement about the contingents of the *Malik* and the *Amīr* is corroborated by circumstantial evidence contained in other sources, yet the actual number of the *sawārs* commanded by a *Khān* does not seem to have been more than five thousand in the 15th century.²¹ Another point to note is that the high nobles who lived at the court in Kalpi kept only a part of their army contingents at the centre, a large number of their army followers staying in their respective *iqṭā's*.²² Putting bits of evidence together, it seems that at that time there were eight *Khāns* and one *Malik* residing in Kalpi, commanding 50,000 *sawārs*. But they seem to have stationed 50 per cent of their army in their respective *iqṭā's*. Therefore, the number of *sawārs* under the nobles staying in Kalpi was in no way higher than 25,000. The sultan also seems to have had a personal force of equal

(19) Baranī, pp. 51-52.

(20) *Masālik al-Abṣār*, Chapters on India, *A Fourteenth Century Arab Account of India under Sultan Muhammad bin Tughluq*, Eng. tr. Iqtidar H. Siddiqui (New Delhi, 1971), p. 38.

(21) Cf. Iqtidar H. Siddiqui, *Some Aspects of Afghan Despotism in India* (Aligarh, 1969), p. xiv.

(22) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 468a.

size in which slaves accounted for the major part.²³ Thus, the cavalry stationed in Kalpi seems to have consisted of 50,000 *sawārs*, and about two hundred thousand persons dependent on them. Besides, there were other servants employed by the sultan and the nobles in different capacities. Apart from the large number of domestic servants, the sultan had a number of petty officials, such as clerks and spies, officially designated as *kārkuns* and *munhiyān* respectively. They were part of the royal establishment.²⁴ The army camp of the sultan, which was a mobile version of his capital, also required the services of a large number of non-military men. Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh and his son and successor, Sultan Qādir Shāh, frequently led plundering expeditions into the neighbouring area and also made conquests. A large number of people were employed to level the ground, pitch *sarāpardah* (royal enclosure) and tents. Moreover, the conquests and successful raids on enemy territories caused a flow of wealth and slaves into Kalpi.²⁵

(23) Some of the royal slaves were raised to the rank of *Malik* and assigned *iqṭā's* independent of the nobles. For instance, Malik Durraj is reported to have been one of those slaves whom Sultan Maḥmūd Turk raised to high positions in his personal army. He was assigned the charge of the *iqṭā'* of Shahpur (*Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 444b). The nobles also assigned important positions to their slaves in their armies and *iqṭā's*. (*Ibid.*, f. 468a.)

(24) The spies were posted in the city of Kalpi as well as in neighbouring areas under the occupation of rival rulers. They supplied information to the sultan about political developments inside the principality and outside. (*Ibid.*, ff. 43^a, 449b.)

(25) The sultan of Kalpi led a number of expeditions for conquest and plunder from time to time. Their victims were both the Hindu chiefs and the Muslim *muqṭā's*, holding towns and *parganahs* in the neighbouring area. They fought a number of battles against the Rā'īs of Etawah, Bath Ghora and Gwalior, but the latter survived on account of their strength and resources. The *muqṭā's* and petty *zamīndārs* were destroyed or made vassals. This state of affairs lasted till the period of turmoil continued. By the year A.D. 1415 a balance of power was established between the sultans in North India. The *zamīndārs* could remain safe by paying allegiance to one or the other sultan as the situation demanded of them. The Sayyid sultans of Delhi and the sultan of Malwa took interest in the survival of Kalpi as a buffer State between them and the sultan of Jaunpur. (See *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 443b, 444a, 445b, 467b; *Ta'rikh-i Mubārak Shāhī*, pp. 207-9, 234; *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī*, pp. 52-54 for the interest shown by the sultans of both Delhi and Malwa in the survival of Kalpi.)

Likewise, the *kārkhānahs* maintained by the sultan and high nobles absorbed a large number of skilled artisans and workers. The interesting pieces of information available in the *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī* reveal that the local court gave impetus to the weaving industry in Kalpi. The sultan is reported to have conferred upon his nobles, *zamīndārs*, 'Ulamā' (religious scholars) and other distinguished residents of the city robes of honour of different types, some of *zarbaft* (cloth woven with silk and gold threads mixed).²⁶ For this purpose, the sultan had a *khil'at-khānah* (big wardrobe) and Ismā'il Khān was in charge of this department.²⁷ The nobles followed this tradition of their master in their *iqṭā's*; they also honoured their officers and *zamīndārs* with *khil'ats* and other rewards.²⁸ This might have encouraged the Muslim weavers to settle down in Kalpi in considerable number. That is why Kalpi became a famous market for textile goods.²⁹ Other important industries that seem to have been established at this time were those of sugar and boat-building. The sugar manufactured in Kalpi was of extreme whiteness and excellent quality. Since Jamuna from Kalpi onward was navigable, Kalpi built large boats and small ships for military purposes.³⁰ The copper mine that continued operating till Akbar's reign might have provided job opportunities to local people.³¹ Similarly the expansion of the city and the building activity provided work to masons and labourers. The use of chiselled stones in the buildings of the period indicates the presence of stone-cutters. Stone seems to have been brought from the quarries in the *iqṭā's* of Jathra and Erachh as both extended upto the range of the Vindhychal. The monuments constructed in Kalpi afford clear evidence of the fusion of

(26) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 439a, 449b.

(27) *Ibid.*, f. 446b.

(28) *Ibid.*, ff. 444a, 449b, 454a, 464a.

(29) Cf. *Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic and Persian Supplement (1953-54), ed. Z. A. Desai (Calcutta), p. 39.

(30) The industry of boat-building continued to flourish in the 16th century also. (*Bāburnāmah*, Eng. tr. Mrs. Beveridge, vol. ii, pp. 598-684.)

(31) Irfan Habib, *An Atlas of the Mughal Empire* (New Delhi, 1982), pp. 8A, 26+80+.

Muslim and Hindu styles, throwing light on the cultural side of the town.³²

The references, contained in different sources, to the traders point to their presence in Kalpi in good number. Actually, the court-generated trade was always an attraction to the merchants and traders. We find the Kalpi traders supplying food grains and other essentials even outside the boundaries of their principality.³³ Here, mention may be made of the liquor-sellers and musicians who seem to have prospered because their product was much in demand. Many nobles had cultivated a taste for alcoholic drinks, as will be shown later.

As regards social life and cultural activities in Kalpi, the relevant evidence available in the contemporary sources tends to show that by the death of Sultan Maḥmūd Turk in A.D. 1412, Kalpi had already turned into a city of light and shade. Side by side with the 'Ulamā', scholars and Sufi saints, the number of those who were fond of pleasure and fine arts considerably increased with the passage of time. The princes and nobles spent lavishly on food, perfumes and on maintaining musicians and dancers in their service. Some of them seem to have patronized the poets along with artists. Their patronage of the artists and poets led to the progress of literature and the arts, such as classical Indian music and dance. The banquets hosted by the princes and nobles in the pleasure gardens and at their residence were attended by musicians, dancing girls and poets. The poets recited their panegyric poems³⁴ in praise of their patrons while the dancers gave performances for the entertainment of the guests assembled there.³⁵ *Akharā*, a

(32) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 437a. See also Y. K. Bukhari, "Some Inscriptions from Kalpi and Jathra," *Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic and Persian Supplement (1953-54), p. 39.

(33) *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī*, p. 37.

(34) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 446b, 447a.

(35) *Ibid.*, 465b; *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī*, p. 49, where Nāṣir Khān, son of Qādir Shāh, is reported to have forced the Muslim girls to get training of dancing and learn the art of music; also *Wāqī'āt-i Mushtāqī* for the popularity of *Akharā* among the nobles.

group dance in which a troupe of dancing girls decked in embroidered silk and adorned with jewels gave a performance with lighted earthen lamps on their palms, held a profound fascination for aristocrats.³⁶ In short, aristocratic aesthetic standards provided a cultural frame for Kalpi.

Another important group of people, who also contributed to the process of urbanization in Kalpi, was that of the 'Ulamā' and Sufis (religious divines). Muḥammad Bihāmad Khānī glows with pride when he describes their arrival in Kalpi and would have us believe that owing to their presence the village of Kalpi and the densely forested area around it, which happened to be the stronghold of infidels, totally unfamiliar with Islamic culture, were soon transformed into an Islamic centre. It does not occur to him, however, that most of the *Sayyids* and 'Ulamā' were worldly people. They took part in court politics and were often found hanging around the court of the sultan or of a noble in the hope of material benefit³⁷; genuine spirituality was the concern of only a few. Nevertheless, their association with the court was valued by the sultan. The 'Ulamā' and Sufis held great influence over the soldiers and the masses, and the patronage extended to them and the interest shown by the sultan in their well-being could increase his popularity. It is true that many scholars and Sufis played an important role in disseminating learning and making Kalpi a seat of culture. We may give an account, here, of a few scholars and leading Sufis who had settled down in Kalpi because their presence in the city enhanced its prestige in medieval times.

The Sufi saints who settled in Kalpi chiefly belonged to the Chishtī and Suhrawardī *silsilahs* (orders). Afterwards, the Zāhidī, Shaṭṭārī and Madārī saints were also attracted by Kalpi's fame. Every one of them tried to turn Kalpi into a centre of their *silsilah*. First, we shall discuss 'Ulamā' and then the Sufis who belonged to different *silsilahs*.

(36) Sikandar b. Muḥammad alias Manjhā, *Mir'āt-i Sikandari*, ed. Satish Chand Misra (Baroda), p. 288, for the description of *Akharā*.

(37) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi*, ff 441b, 451ab.

The most famous of the scholars was Bandagī Malik al-'Ulamā' wa al-Fuḍalā' Mawlānā Humām Aḥmad Thānesari, celebrated for his mastery over both prose and verse. He was the *Dabir-i Khāṣṣ* under Sultan Firūz Shāh and is said to have drafted most of the letters on behalf of the sultan to Amīr Timūr, the ruler of central Asia. "He left *Qubbāt al-Islām* Ḥaḍrat-i Dihlī after the invasion of Timūr and settled in this auspicious city." Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh Turk provided him with the comforts and necessities of life. Many people including Aḥmad Khān, the brother of Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh Turk, became his disciples. On his death, Aḥmad Khān constructed a grand mausoleum on his grave the lofty dome of which filled visitors with wonder.³⁸ Another famous scholar, Mawlānā Shāms al-Dīn, known as Naḥwī, who had no rival in learning and sophistication, also sought asylum in Kalpi. On his death he was buried outside the fortification of the city and a tomb was erected over his grave.³⁹ According to the author of the *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi*, the city of Muḥammadabad (alias Kalpi) rose in dignity and gained wide fame on account of the shrines of these two pious scholars.⁴⁰

Likewise, Bandagī Shaykhzādah 'Alī, Mawlānā Muḥammad Thānesari who had got the title of *Malik al-'Ulamā'* in Ḥaḍrat-i Dihlī, and Mawlānā Ashraf Sāmī, all recognized as leading scholars of their age, joined the court of the sultan and received royal favours.⁴¹ Mawlānā

(38) *Ibid*, ff 442b-443a.

(39) *Ibid.*, f. 443a.

(40) *Ibid.*, f. 442b. The authors of *Akḥbār al-Akhyār* and *Gulzār-i Abrār* say, perhaps on the basis of later traditions, that they were the *khilāfahs* of Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn Chirāgh. But their statements are not supported by the contemporary source, *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi*. As Mawlānā Humām Aḥmad held the government post in Delhi, he was not fit for *khilāfah*. Shaykh Nizām al-Dīn Awliyā' and Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn considered association with the royal court injurious to spiritual life. They did not confer *khilāfah* on those who held any post at the royal court. But Shaikh Abdul Latif accepts their statements. (Cf. "A Study of the Muslim Saints of Kalpi," *Indian History Congress*, Proceedings of the 38th Session, 1972, pp. 337-38.)

(41) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi*, f. 443a.

Ashrāf Sāmī was also a *khalīfah* of Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn Chirāgh of Delhi.⁴²

The hagiographic sources add to the information available in the *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi* about the early Sufi saints of Kalpi. Their inclusion by Shaykh 'Abd al-Ḥaqq Muḥaddith Dihlawī in his biographical work is indicative of the fact that they were eminent Sufi scholars of their age. Among them, Mawlānā Aḥmad Thānesarī, son of Mawlānā Muḥammad Thānesarī settled in Kalpi along with his family and followers in the beginning of the 15th century. A disciple of Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn Chirāgh of Delhi, he had also acquired wide fame for his mastery over different Islamic sciences including Ḥanafite *fiqh* (jurisprudence). He imparted instruction in Islamic jurisprudence and popularized the teachings of the Chishtī *silsilah* by accepting *murīds*.⁴³

A few distinguished disciples and *khalīfahs* of Sayyid Muḥammad Gīsūdirāz (the *khalīfah* of Shaykh Naṣīr al-Dīn Chirāgh) also settled in Kalpi. For example, Shaykh 'Alā' al-Dīn Qurayshī and Shaykh Abū al-Faṭḥ 'Alā'ī Qurayshī were two leading Chishtī saints who settled in Kalpi, sometime after the invasion of Timūr. The former hailed from Gwalior. He generally lived in seclusion, spending his time in prayer to God.⁴⁴ The latter lived in the midst of the people, wrote a number of treatises on Sufism and taught his disciples esoteric as well as exoteric sciences.⁴⁵ After his death, his rich disciples built a grand tomb over his grave in 1450. This tomb is built of stone and brick in lime and covered over with lime plaster. Its lofty dome raised on an octagonal drum is bulbous. The inscription on the southern doorway calls him *Zā'ir al-Ḥaramayn* (one who paid visit to the *ḥarams* [holy places] in Mecca and Medina).⁴⁶

(42) *Ibid.*, ff. 161ab.

(43) *Akhbār al-Akhyār*, ed. Shaikh Zafar Ali (Ahmadi Press, Delhi, n.d.), p. 166.

(44) *Ibid.*, pp. 185, 188.

(45) *Ibid.*

(46) Cf. *Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic and Persian Supplement (1953-54), pp. 35-36.

The important Suhrawardī saint who won followers among various sections of people in Kalpi was Shaykh Sirāj Sokhtah. He was also a profound scholar. First he committed the Qur'ān to memory, and then studied other popular sciences of his time. For his deep learning, he was included among the distinguished pupils of Mawlānā Naḥwī like Qādī Shihāb al-Dīn Dawlatābādī. It was due to his learning that Shaykh Jalāl al-Dīn Bukhārī, popularly known as Jahāniyān-i Jahāngasht, selected him as one of his *khalīfahs*. After his arrival in Kalpi, he became one of the most respectable Sufis of the city. Sultan Qādir Shāh, son and successor of Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh (A.D. 1411-1432), held him in high esteem.⁴⁷

Another Suhrawardī saint of eminence was Shaykh Yūsuf Budā Erachhī. He was also the disciple of Makhdūm-i Jahāniyān-i Jahāngasht. A distinguished scholar of Arabic, known for his mastery over Islamic doctrinal and Sufi texts, high literary ability and a refined sensibility for poetry, Erachhī had become one of the most popular and respected Sufis of North India. He is credited with having written a number of books. His translation of Imām Ghazālī's *Minhāj al-'Abidīn* in *mathnawī* form, consisting of two thousand five hundred and twenty verses and entitled *Fatūḥāt-i Aḥmad*, was as popular as his *dīwān* (the collection of poems). Like the Chishtī Sufis, he was also fond of *samā'* (audition party) and considered it as a means of spiritual development. In 1430 he attended a *samā'* party in which he passed into an ecstatic state. He remained in this state of mystic intoxication for several days and then passed away in Erachh. It should at the same time be pointed out that the biographical notices contained in the *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi* tend to show that the Shaykh was never negligent of social obligations incumbent upon a Sufi of his eminence. He took his duty of instructing his *murīds* (disciples) seriously and maintained the traditions of his *silsilah*.⁴⁸ Maḥmūd Khān (son of

(47) *Akhbār al-Akhyār*, p. 188.

(48) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi*, ff. 169b-173b.

Mughith Khān), later Sultan 'Alā' al-Dīn Maḥmūd Shāh Khalji of Malwa, had a mausoleum constructed over his grave.⁴⁹

As regards the Zāhidi *silsilah*, Shaykh Bahā' al-Dīn Ganj-i Rawān introduced it in Kalpi during the reign of Sultan Qādir Shāh. Both the members of the ruling elite and the commoners had faith in him. Ghawthī Shaṭṭārī informs us that the sultan and his officers offered him cash, villages and gardens but he never accepted any gift from them. Nevertheless, he fed a large number of people daily and for this reason was called by the people *Ganj-i Rawān* (ever-flowing reservoir). He occupied an unclaimed tract of land on the bank of the Jamuna towards the end of his life and carried on cultivation there. He also built a house and planted a garden. The spiritual qualities, possessed by him to an impressive degree, helped his successors to keep their *silsilah* alive after him.⁵⁰

Similarly, the founder of the Madārī *silsilah* in India, Shaykh Badī' al-Dīn, popularly known as Shāh Madār, came to Kalpi during the reign of Qādir Shāh. He was a Syrian Sufi of Jewish origin. On his conversion to Islam, he got himself enrolled among the disciples of Shaykh Ṭayfūr Shāmī. He acquired mastery over Ibn 'Arabī's metaphysical doctrine, known as *waḥdat al-wujūd*, in addition to his knowledge of Jewish and Christian mystical practices. However, the paucity of authentic information about him makes it somewhat difficult to attempt a detailed study of his life and teachings. Some 17th-century writers, such as 'Abd al-Raḥmān Chishtī, the author of *Mir'āt-i Madāriyah* and the compiler of *Dabistān al-Madhāhib*, have confused historical traditions with fiction and incorporated in their works all that they found floating down the stream of time. In fact, they wrote their works when the followers of the Madārī *silsilah* had begun to indulge in all sorts of vices in complete disregard of the teachings of the great Shaykh. The odd bits pieced from different standard works reveal that he was respected and generally held by orthodox

(49) *Ibid.*, ff. 174, 174a; *Akhbār al-Akhyār*, p. 178. Erāchh is included in the district of Jhansi in Uttar Pradesh.

(50) *Gulzār-i Abrār*, Urdu tr., pp. 192-99.

Sufis to be in the first rank of the Indian Muslim Sufis. He commanded great respect among people for his religiosity and piety and was never opposed to the observance of Muslim rituals. For instance, a contemporary inscription found in a step-well in Chanderi, dated 1436, mentions the builder of the well, Taghi, the learned vizir at the court of Malwa, along with his *Pīr*, Shāh Madār. The latter has been mentioned as "the great, pious and religious-minded saint."⁵¹ Likewise, the references to Shāh Madār contained in the *malfūzāt* of the 15th-century Sufi saints tend to show that the leading Chishtī saints held him in high esteem. The 16th-century historian Badā'ūnī also incorporates a few anecdotes in his *Najāt al-Rashīd*, showing that he also had no doubts about Shāh Madār being a pious Sufi.*

In Kalpi, Shāh Madār got into touch with the Hindu Yogis and seems to have discussed with them the Yoga philosophy. The testimony of Shaykh 'Abd al-Ḥaqq Muḥaddith of Delhi is significant in this regard. According to him, Shāh Madār was very fond of the company of the Yogis and discussed with them problems relating Hindu mysticism.⁵² The association of the Sufis with the Yogis was not objectionable during the 15th century. Some of the leading Chishtī saints also adopted certain Yogic practices. For instance, Shaykh 'Abd al-Ḥaqq Rudawlī and 'Abd al-Quddūs Gangohī regularly did the exercises of controlling breath, burying themselves alive or offering devotions while hanging head down suspended by a rope tied to the heels.⁵³

A few words may be added about Shāh Madār's departure from Kalpi to the Sharqi Kingdom of Jaunpur. It is said that he refused to receive Qādir Shāh of Kalpi who was desirous of calling on him. Feeling insulted, the sultan asked Shāh Madār to leave his territory.

(51) *Cf. Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic and Persian Supplement, ed. Z.A. Desai, 1966, p. 68.

(52) *Akhbār al-Akhyār*, p. 188.

(53) *Cf. Simon Degby*, "Abdul Quddus Gangohi: The Personality and Attitudes of a Medieval Indian Sufi," *Medieval India - A Miscellany*, vol. 3 (Aligarh, 1975), pp. 36-39.

* 'Abd al-Qādir Badā'ūnī, *Najāt al-Rashīd*, ed. Syed Moinul Haq (Lahore, 1972), p. 173.

Thereupon Shāh Madār went to Jaunpur and finally settled down in Makanpur,⁵⁴ a small town now included in the district of Kanpur. One of his disciples and successors, Qāḍī Maẓhar, however, stayed in Kalpi. Ghawthī Shaṭṭārī states that Qāḍī Maẓhar was an 'Alim and a devout Sufi, sincerely devoted to the cause of religion.⁵⁵

Another scholarly Sufi who flourished in Kalpi during the 15th-16th centuries was Shaykh Burhān Anṣārī. Devoted to religion and piety, he always preferred a life of abject poverty to that of comfort. He spent his time either in offering prayers in his cell or imparting knowledge of religious lore. In his public lectures that he delivered daily, he explained the significance of the Qur'ānic verses. Mullā 'Abd al-Qāḍir Badā'ūnī paid visit to him in Kalpi and found him more than a hundred years old.⁵⁶ People considered him a Mahdawī but Ghawthī Shaṭṭārī states that this charge was not borne out by facts. Shaykh Burhān Anṣārī composed verses in Hindawi, as well as in Persian. His *dīwān*, entitled *Firāq-nāmāh*, was available in the 17th century. Praising it, Ghawthī Shaṭṭārī says that every line of the *dīwān* is full of pathos and marked by intensity of feeling.⁵⁷

Kalpi's Hinterland and Satellite Towns :

The entire area within the boundaries of the principality formed the hinterland of the city of Kalpi. The *iqṭā's* and *parganahs*, mentioned by the medieval writers, help identify its frontiers. For example, the *parganah* of Chaurasi,⁵⁸ that lay on the boundary of the *Khittāh-i Qil'ah-i Qanauj* (later included in the modern district of Farukhabad

(54) *Akhbār al-Akhyār*, p. 188.

(55) *Gulzār-i Abrār*, Urdu tr., p. 77.

(56) *Muntakhab al-Tawārikh*, vol. iii, pp. 6-7.

(57) *Gulzār-i Abrār*, Urdu tr., p. 305.

(58) Muḥammad Bihāmad Khānī says that his father was assigned the charge of the *parganah* of Chaurasi in 1393-94. After his posting, he cleaned it of the contumacious elements and also seized several villages that were included in the territorial unit of the Fort of Qanauj. (*Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 467a.)

U. P.), the *parganahs* of Baladar,⁵⁹ Sugandpur,⁶⁰ Adampur⁶¹ (in Etawah), Kakura,⁶² Chachawali,⁶³ and Dirapur⁶⁴ included in the *iqṭā'* of Shahpur⁶⁵ (now in Kanpur district of U.P.) constituted its northern frontier. These *parganahs* comprised parts of the modern districts of Farukhabad, Ettah and Etawah, and shared borders with the Sharqi territorial units of Qanauj, Kara and Manikpur,⁶⁶ and with the *zamīndārī* of the Chauhan ruler, Rā'i Ṣābir of Etawah.⁶⁷ The eastern *iqṭā'* of Mahoba extended over the area upto the boundaries of the regions under the rule of the Rā'is of Kalinjar and Bath Ghora.⁶⁸ The southern frontier was bound by the *iqṭā's* of Jathra and Bhandar that

(59) *Bāburnāmāh*, vol. ii, pp. 649, 650, for the *parganahs* including the *sarkār* of Kalpi in the beginning of the 16th century. Neither the Lodis nor Bābur made any alteration in the size of the unit as will be shown later.

(60) *Ibid.*

(61) *Ibid.*

(62) *Ibid.*

(63) *Ibid.*

(64) *Ibid.*

(65) The *iqṭā'* of Shahpur was held by Malik Durraj, one of the chief slaves of Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh of Kalpi.

(66) The towns of Jajmau and Kanpur formed part of the administrative unit of Kara and Manikpur. It shows that the region of the modern district of Kanpur was included in the *shiqqs* of both Kara and Kalpi. (Cf. Iqtidar A. Siddiqui, "Evolution of the vilayet, the shiqq, and the sarkar," *Medieval India Quarterly*, vol. 5, 1963, Aligarh, p. 29 [f. n. 5].)

(67) The relations between the sultan of Kalpi and the Chauhan ruler of Etawah, Rā'i Ṣābir, were strained in the beginning. There remained a constant conflict of arms between them and they fought a number of battles for the control of border *parganahs*. On Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh's death, Rā'i Ṣābir made compromise with Qāḍir Shāh (son of Sultan Maḥmūd Turk) in 1413. Since then they remained allies and lent military support to each other whenever need arose. (*Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 443b, 444a, 448a, b.)

(68) Mahoba was the headquarters of one of the important *iqṭā's* in the principality of Kalpi. As it was exposed to raids by the chief of Bath Ghora, a rival, Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh constructed a very lofty, impregnable fort with a strong *ḥiṣār* (walls) all around. On its completion he posted there Muzaffar Khān bin Mukarram Khān with a strong force. (*Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, f. 439a.)

comprised the area upto the boundary of the Malwa territory of Chanderi.⁶⁹ The western frontier was bound by the *iqṭā'* of Erachh (in Jhansi district of U.P.) that included the entire area running parallel to the region of the principalities of Gwalior and Bayana.⁷⁰

Besides the aforesaid border *iqṭā's* and *parganahs*, there were old and newly-carved out *parganahs*, lying inside the frontiers of the principality. Undoubtedly, the information available in our sources is very inadequate; only the military conquests and expeditions, rebellions and their suppression by the sultan find a detailed description. Despite this, one may sift enough evidence of the construction of fortresses, *hiṣārs* (fortification) and bazars in the old and newly-founded towns. For example, the first place captured by the ruler of Kalpi was the small locality of Khandant⁷¹ that belonged to the *zamīndārī* of Rā'i Bahrāj, the *zamīndār* of Hamirpur. The sultan fortified Khandant, built a palace-fortress and named it Maḥmūdābād after his own name. The author of the *Ta'riḫ-i Muḥammadī* informs us that due to the interest taken by the sultan in its development, Mahmudabad emerged as a city of Islam.⁷² Likewise, references contained in our sources to the *parganah* of Chhaparghatta (twenty miles from Kalpi) town of Ratha⁷³ and the town of Chakni⁷⁴ tend to reveal that these were

(69) Jathra lies in 25° 1' N and 79° 6' E, in the Tikamgarh district, M.P. Bhandar is the headquarters of a *parganah* in the Bhind district, M.P., sit. 25° 44' N, 78° 45' E.

(70) The *iqṭā'* of Erachh was one of the most important units in the principality. Formerly, the *iqṭā'* of Erachh was held by Malik Sulaymān. Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh of Kalpi seized it with the help of Dilāwar Khān of Malwa in the beginning of the 15th century. First he brought it under *khālīṣah* but soon later assigned it to his brother Khān-i A'zam Junayd Khān, the vizir of Kalpi. It comprised the entire area of the modern district of Jhansi and a portion of Gwalior district. (*Ta'riḫ-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 440ab, 442a.)

(71) Khandant is still in the district of Hamirpur, U.P.

(72) *Ta'riḫ-i Muḥammadī*, f. 438a.

(73) It is a *taḥṣīl* headquarters in the district of Hamirpur, U.P., sit. 25° 36' N, 79° 34' E, fifty miles south-west of Hamirpur. It was held by Malik Ibrāhīm Rāzi, one of the trusted nobles of the sultan.

(74) *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī*, p. 60.

fortified and economically developed during this period. Equally important was the tendency among the *muḥṭā's* to increase the income of their *iqṭā's* by clearing jungles, founding villages and establishing *thhānahs*⁷⁵ (military outposts) for the protection of the roads and villages. The *thhānahs* had the full potential to develop into towns. Many of them became flourishing towns in the 16th century.⁷⁶

Mention may here be made of the revenue accruing to the ruler of Kalpi from the dense forests that existed on its western and eastern borders. The availability of timber gave rise to the boat-building industry in Kalpi as already mentioned. Moreover, herds of wild elephants in the forests attracted the elephant-catchers who settled along Kalpi's border villages, numbering thirty to forty. They paid tax directly on every catch to the royal exchequer. The elephants caught were sold in the neighbouring cities. Bābur says that the value and price of an elephant were judged on the basis of its height and size. The larger it was, the higher was its price.⁷⁷

We may now briefly discuss the increase in population and the development in urban and rural areas. The network of roads built by the rulers for linking different towns and *parganahs* with one another and with capital, and connecting Kalpi with the neighbouring kingdoms, gave a new aspect to the economic set-up in the region. The relevant evidence available in the *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī* sheds light on the socio-economic growth in the area. The towns of Mahoba and Shahpur are reported to have become centres of trade, and of

(75) Muḥammad Bihāmad Khān enlightens us on this point when he describes his own achievements in his *Ta'riḫ*. He says that Bihāmad Khān, the deputy of the vizir, built a strong fort along with *hiṣār* at the village of Koeth in the *iqṭā'* of Erachh in 1430. He also established *thhānahs* and assigned their charge to officers designated as *thhānahdārs* for its protection against the dacoits. (*Ta'riḫ-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 474a-b.)

(76) Emperor Akbar divided the vast *sarkār* of Kalpi into two *sarkārs*, *sarkār* of Kalpi and *sarkār* of Erachh. (Abū al-Faḍl, *A'in-i Akbarī*, Eng. tr. Colonel H. S. Jarrett, [New Delhi, reprint, 1978], vol. ii, pp. 195, 198-99.)

(77) *Bāburnāmah*, vol. ii, p. 488.

Islamic learning and culture owing to the presence in them of scholars and *Sayyids*. We also learn that necessary steps were taken for safeguarding the roads against highwaymen.⁷⁸

The limited resources of the principality, surrounded by the kingdoms of Delhi, Jaunpur and Malwa, led the sultan to take interest in the extension of cultivation, as it was the main source of income to the State. As a result, the forests were cleared and villages were founded. These measures seem to have considerably increased the financial resources of the State. For example, the *parganah* of Chaurasi that had long lain desolate became so prosperous within a short time due to efforts made by the officers that its revenue was doubled. It began to yield one lakh *tankahs*.⁷⁹ Likewise, Jathra, a small town without a fort in the 14th century, developed into a beautiful city. It was assigned by the sultan to Nizām Khān, his second brother, as maintenance-*iqṭā'*. Since that time Jathra continued to be held by Nizām Khān's descendants for generations. Majlis-i 'Alī Nizām Khān and his descendants beautified it with buildings and planted gardens and orchards outside the city walls.⁸⁰ Moreover, epigraphical evidence shows that in Jathra certain arts and crafts also developed. In any case, Jathra became famous for wine-manufacturing and for its musicians. The *khammārs* (liquor-sellers and manufacturers) and *kalāwants* (musicians) grew very rich, acquiring aristocratic habits. They spent money on the construction of buildings of public utility and had inscriptions in Persian fixed on them in imitation of the members of the ruling elite.⁸¹ The wine industry led to the extension of grape cultivation

(78) *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī*, p. 49.

(79) *Ta'riḫ-i Muḥammadī*, f. 467a.

(80) *Ibid.*, f. 465b.

(81) There have been found two Persian inscriptions fixed on two stepped-wells. One assigns the construction of the big well to Bholā Mahārāj Khammār (a liquor-seller) who resided in Jathra. It is dated 24th February A. D. 1436. The other records the construction of the stepped-well by Shyam Kunwar Kalāwant (musician) in A. D. 1500-01. The first was completed in the days of Khān-i A'zam, Ismā'il Khān, son of Nizām Khān. According to the second inscription, the chief of Jathra was Khān-i A'zam Tatar Khān, son of Muḥammad, the latter being the grandson of Nizām Khān. (Cf. *Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic and Persian Supplement [1953-54], pp. 39-41.)

all around Jathra. We can also assume, on the basis of this information, that socio-economic development was not only horizontal but vertical, at least to some extent.

The *iqṭā'* and city of Erachh also merit discussion for their economic development during the period under review. The town of Erachh had been the headquarters of an *iqṭā'* since the 14th century. It had one of the strongest forts of North India and was full of *ashrāf*, i.e. the elite.⁸² Erachh developed from a town into a city after its annexation by Sultan Maḥmūd Shāh. The sultan gave it to his brother, Khān-i A'zam Junayd Khān, the vizir, in *iqṭā'*. The vizir and, later, his sons made all possible efforts to raise it to the size and importance of Kalpi itself. They made generous land-grants to scholars and *Mashā'ikhs* invited artisans from different places and gave them all the facilities for their permanent settlement. They expanded the town by building new quarters and bazars. For its defence, an outer fortification was raised in addition to the inner walls.⁸³ The Jāmi' mosque constructed by the vizir, Junayd Khān, in Erachh in A. D. 1408 bears testimony to the building activity there. The inscription points to the considerable increase in the population of the town, which rendered the old mosque insufficient for Friday congregations. The *qāḍī* of Erachh, Ḍiyā' al-Dīn, therefore persuaded the *Wālī* to construct a new and more spacious mosque.⁸⁴ The tombs built over the graves of Khwājah Ikhtiyār al-Dīn 'Umar Erachhī⁸⁵ (d. A. D. 1406) and Shaykh Yūsuf Būdā⁸⁶ (d. A. D. 1430) are worth mentioning. The tomb over the grave of the former was built by the ruler of Kalpi. The tomb of Shaykh Yūsuf Būdā was

(82) *Ta'riḫ-i Muḥammadī*, f. 442a.

(83) *Ibid.*, ff. 472a, 474a-b.

(84) Cf. *Annual Report on Indian Epigraphy*, 1963-64, No. 367, Appendix D.

(85) He was the *murīd* (disciple) and *khalīfah* (spiritual vicegerent) of Shaykh Naṣir al-Dīn Chiragh of Delhi. (*Ta'riḫ-i Muḥammadī*, f. 162a.)

(86) He was the *murīd* and pupil of Khwājah Ikhtiyār al-Dīn 'Umar. Later on, he became the *khalīfah* of Shaykh Rājū Qattāl of the Suhrawardī order. A distinguished scholar, he left a number of books including a *diwān*. (*Ta'riḫ-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 165-170a; *Akhbār al-Akhyār*, p. 178.)

built by Sultan Maḥmūd Khaljī of Malwa who happened to be one of his disciples as mentioned above. According to both Muḥammad Bihāmad Khānī and Shaykh 'Abd al-Ḥaqq Dihlawī, its lofty dome had no match in height and beauty in the neighbouring territories.

Social Relations :

The evidence, accessible to us in the historical and hagiographical sources, about social relations between the members of different communities and social groups, though scanty, is still quite interesting. It points to a spirit of mutual understanding and cooperation among the people. In fact, two centuries of co-existence seems to have brought Hindus and Muslims together, narrowing down their social and cultural differences. Both, the Sufis and the Yogis stood for pulling down of social barriers between various culture-groups.⁸⁷ As in other cities and towns in the early period, the Sufis and the Yogis lived in peace and amity in Kalpi, discussed spiritual matters to one another's benefit and initiated trends of social importance that shaped the cultural pattern of society and influenced people's attitudes towards life and humanity. In short, the impression created by the hagiographic and historical literature is that the 15th century in North India was marked by the revival of Islamic orthodoxy and the rise of syncretic trends and the popularity of eclecticism.⁸⁸ The fourth ruler of Kalpi, Nāṣir Shāh bin Qādir Shāh, is reported by medieval writers to have abandoned the path of orthodoxy and adopted practices of heretics. This implies

(87) The doors of the *khānqāhs* of the Muslim Sufis were thrown open to all people irrespective of creed. Hindus and Muslims paid visit to the Sufis for their blessings. The information contained in the collections of the sayings (*malfuzāt*) of the Sufis reflects on their humanism and catholicity of views that shaped their attitude towards people regardless of religion. (Cf. Iqtidar H. Siddiqui, *Modern Writings on Islam and Muslims in India* [Aligarh, 1972], pp. 21-24.)

Ibn Baṭṭūṭah furnished interesting details about the popularity of the Yogis among the Muslims from the King down to the beggar. He says : "Many Mussalmans follow them [Yogis] in order to take lessons from them." (*The Rehla*, Eng. tr. Mahdi Husain [Baroda, 1953], p. 166.)

(88) *Akḥbār al-Akhyār*, pp. 188-89.

that he was deeply influenced by the syncretic movements and thought of the day. He was severely resisted and condemned by the orthodox Muslims in Kalpi.⁸⁹

It may be pointed out that the details furnished by Muḥammad Bihāmad Khānī about the religious policy of his patrons, the sultans of Kalpi, fail to provide a true picture of the age. He would have us believe that in every village and town the Muslim conquest was followed by the suppression of Hindu practices and the introduction of the Islamic customs instead.⁹⁰ This is not corroborated by the circumstantial evidence available even in his own *Ta'rikh*, wherein the rulers seem to have re-ordered their relations with the Hindu *zamīndārs* who had deep-rooted local control of land and peasants.⁹¹ The latter acquiesced in the sultan's authority when he left them untouched, with complete autonomy in the area of their *zamīndāris*. There is no dearth of information to show that these *zamīndārs* were invited to social functions held at the royal court and honoured with precious gifts and robes. In return, they rendered military service at the time of need, paid *khidmatī* (a Hindawī equivalent of Persian *peškhāsh*) along with annual *kharāj*.⁹² We may also add the information available about the intertribal conflict and feuds that were common among the Rajput

(89) Muḥammad Qasim Firishtah, *Ta'rikh-i Firishtah* (Nawal Kishore edition), vol. iii, p. 247.

(90) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammauī*, f. 437a, 438a, 438b.

(91) Here, cases of Rā'i Bhairāj of Hamirpur *pargana*, Bhilam, the *muqaddam* of Sinehal, Rā'i Kalyān of Samoni (all holding *zamīndāris*) in the region between the Kalpi's *iqā'* of Mahoba and the territory of Bath Ghora (modern Rewa) may be referred to. They resisted the expansion of Sultan Maḥmūd's rule in the beginning and then became his trusted vassals after they had failed to achieve success. (*Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadi*, ff. 438, 439a-b.)

(92) *Ibid.*, ff. 444a. The term *khidmatī* was synonymous with Persian *peškhāsh* that in Mughal times a noble or chief had to offer to the Mughal Emperor. Muḥammad Bihāmad Khānī is not the only writer of the pre-Mughal period to use it. 'Diyā' al-Dīn Baranī and Yaḥyā Sirhindī also use it in the same sense (Baranī, pp. 577-78; *Ta'rikh-i Mubārak Shāhī*, p. 184). Shihāb Ḥakīm also uses *khidmatī* in the sense of offering. (*Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhī*, p. 52.)

chiefs in this region. People suffered much from this internecine strife. The case of Rā'i Šābir of Etawah is a case in point. He was hostile to the Raja of Bhogaon, also a Rajput chief, belonging to the Bhaduriya branch of the Chauhan tribe. The latter had succeeded in building up a tiny principality that embraced portions of Mainpuri, Farrukhabad and Etah districts. For his destruction, Rā'i Šābir Chauhan accepted allegiance to Qādir Shāh of Kalpi and persuaded him to invade Bhogaon. The joint armies of Etawah and Kalpi are reported to have done great damage to the Rā'i of Bhogaon by ravaging most of his principality in 1413. Had Sultan Ibrāhīm Sharqī not marched against Kalpi, they would have completely destroyed Bhogaon, the author of *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī* informs us.⁹³ In this way the rise of regional powers led to the establishment of peace, as the chiefs accepted the overlordship of someone among the sultans who could protect them against other rulers.

As regards the increase in Muslim population in the region, low caste conversions at least to some extent, combined with the process of urbanization, were responsible for it. In the towns and cities the *khānqāhs* of the Sufi saints attracted Muslims and Hindus alike. They visited the Sufis with different personal problems, psychological as well as economic, and sought their blessing. Impressed by their piety and spiritual qualities individual Hindus adopted the Islamic faith and then became devout Muslims under their influence.⁹⁴ The slaves purchased by the Muslim aristocrats added to the number of Muslims in urban centres. The slave boys and girls were brought up like Muslims.⁹⁵ Even the 'Ulamā' possessed slaves—both male and female. However, the sultans and nobles never appear to have taken interest in the conversion of unwilling non-Muslims to Islam.

We may briefly discuss here rural-urban relations as these cast light on the concern that Muslim rulers had for the economic development

(93) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 449v-45-a.

(94) *Akhbār al-Akhyār*, pp. 209-255; *Lafā'if-i Quddāsī* (Muḥtabā'i Press, Delhi), pp. 57-58.

(95) *Wāqī'āt-i Mushtāqī*, f. 30a.

of the countryside. We have definite evidence revealing the close ties established by the members of the ruling elite with the rural people in the area. A contemporary historian, who was himself a part of the ruling class, emphasizes over and over again the fact that the sultans took pains in promoting the general good, and people owed allegiance to the dynasty out of gratefulness for the good done to them by the rulers.⁹⁶ Likewise, the *muqī'as* whose *iqṭā's* were seldom transferred came into direct contact with the peasants and encouraged them to extend the area of cultivation by clearing forests and ploughing fallow land. Most probably the small size of the territory and its limited resources forced the ruling class to adopt this policy.

The close ties, existing between the urban centres and the villages, are also discernible in the details about the decoration and illumination of the city carried out by the citizens for welcoming the sultan, or an army general on his successful return from a military campaign, or for celebrating the births and marriages of princes. Such occasions provided people with an opportunity for general rejoicing in the city and the *havelī* (suburb).⁹⁷ But there is no direct evidence to show the reaction of people living in remote villages. A few anecdotes in the *Wāqī'āt-i Mushtāqī* show that village women usually came out of their villages, singing songs to welcome the army from their side. The generals used to distribute money to them.⁹⁸

Nevertheless, there was a great deal of scorn among the urbans for the rustics. 'Iṣāmī calls the latter impure demons, unworthy of taking the place of the former in any walk of life. Comparing the two he goes to the extent of calling people of the city nightingales and those of villages no better than owls.⁹⁹ The evidence available in the *Ta'rikh-i Mubārak Shāhī* shows that in the city people made fun of the

(96) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 442b.

(97) *Ibid.*, ff. 465b-466a.

(98) *Wāqī'āt-i Mushtāqī*, ff. 35a-b, 40a.

(99) 'Iṣāmī, *Futūḥ al-Salāṭīn*, ed. Usha (Madras, n.d.).

villagers for their simplicity or lack of urbanity.¹⁰⁰ The same attitude can be seen in the anecdotes narrated by Shaykh Rizq Allāh Mushtāqī, wherein a villager can easily be made out from others on account of his rusticity.¹⁰¹ The townsfolk do not seem to have realized that most of their urban amenities depended on the supply of produce from the countryside and the grandeur of their cities was sustained, to a large extent, by the revenue levied on agriculture.

The role played by the land-grant holders and the primary *zamīndārs*, who acted as intermediaries between the urban-based State and the peasantry, may also be analyzed briefly. As we have dealt with this problem at length elsewhere,¹⁰² we need not go into details here. It may, however, be stressed that the distinct practice of the land-grant holders from the 14th century onwards was to develop on their land a series of gardens and orchards with beautiful villas inside.¹⁰³ The urban culture penetrated the countryside through the land-grant holders and the primary *zamīndārs*. At the same time it may be stated that it was not at all a one way traffic. The aristocratic customs of the landed gentry seem to have influenced the urbanized nobility of the Sultanate period.¹⁰⁴ People bowed low before the noble as villagers humbled themselves before the Chaudhri. Similarly, the rural basis of the medieval urban crafts, such as weaving and boat-building in Kalpi, may be pointed out but need not be explained in detail as it is common knowledge.

Finally, something may be said about the period during which the principality enjoyed absolute independence. It continued to exist as a buffer to the sultanates of Delhi, Jaunpur and Malwa till 1442.

(100) *Ta'rikh-i Mubarak Shāhi*, p. 95.

(101) *Wāqī'at-i Mushtāqī*.

(102) See Iqtidar H. Siddiqui, *History of Sher Shāh Sur* (Aligarh, 1971), where I have analyzed the nature of land-grants during the Sultanate period.

(103) *Ibid.*

(104) Referring to the Mongol prisoners, 'Iṣāmī says: "They belittled themselves before every soldier of the royal army in the same way, as people belittle themselves before the Hindu Chaudhri." (*Futūḥ al-Salāṭīn*)

During this period it survived two invasions by Sultan Ibrāhīm Sharqī of Jaunpur. At the time of the first Sharqī invasion in 1413 Sultan Hoshang Shāh came to Kalpi's rescue.¹⁰⁵ In 1432-33, when the second invasion took place after the death of Qādir Shāh, both Sultan Mubārak Shāh of Delhi and Hoshang Shāh marched from their respective capitals against Sultan Ibrāhīm Sharqī. As a result, Kalpi was saved and Jalāl Khān (son of Qādir Shāh) remained unaffected.¹⁰⁶ The course of later events suggests that the aim of the Sharqī sultan was limited; instead of a full conquest he wanted the ruler of Kalpi to pay allegiance to him. But his rivals wanted Kalpi to exist as a buffer State between them.

In the year 1442 the situation took an unfavourable turn against the ruling dynasty. By this time, Sultan Maḥmūd Sharqī had already won over the Kalpi nobility and the *ashrāf* (urban social elite among the Muslims) to his side through bribe. Assured of their support, he sent his envoy to the court of Sultan Maḥmūd Khaljī of Malwa with precious gifts and 29 elephants as an offering. The Sharqī envoy, having presented the gifts, conveyed the verbal message of his master, that Nāṣir Khān-i Jahān, son of Qādir Shāh (the fourth ruler of Kalpi), had abandoned the path of Islamic orthodoxy and was harming the interests of Muslims and Islam. He had given Muslim girls to Hindus for being trained as dancers and musicians, and he should either be corrected through punishment by the Malwa court or the Jaunpur sultan be permitted to set him right. The gifts had the desired effect on the Malwa sultan. The latter gave permission to the Sharqī sultan to punish the ruler of Kalpi for his misconduct.¹⁰⁷

(105) Sultan Ibrāhīm Sharqī is reported to have appeared before the gates of Kalpi with his entire army, elephants and war machines, *manjanīqs* and catapults. He struggled for more than two months but failed to capture the city. In fact, the army of Kalpi enabled Qādir Shāh to defend him successfully. Being disappointed, Sultan Ibrāhīm Sharqī made peace with Kalpi and left for Jaunpur. (*Ta'rikh-i Mubarak Shāhi*, p. 180; *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 451a-b.)

(106) *Ta'rikh-i Muḥammadī*, ff. 457a-b, 458a-b, 459a; *Ta'rikh-i Mubarak Shāhi*, pp. 207-9, 234.

(107) *Ma'āthir-i Maḥmūd Shāhi*, pp. 49, 52, 54, 59.

On the Sharqī occupation of Kalpi and its dependencies, Nāṣir Khān approached the Malwa court, pleading not guilty and saying that Sultan Maḥmūd Sharqī had arrested Muslims, and had confiscated their property as that of the infidels in *Dār al-Ḥarb* (non-Muslim territory), and that his allies were Hindus, such as the Rā'is of Bath Ghora and Bhakesar.¹⁰⁸ Sultan Maḥmūd Khaljī (A. D. 1436-1469) wrote a letter to the Sharqī sultan asking him to restore the territory of Kalpi to Nāṣir Khān as it was his ancestral possession and as he had repented for his past lapses and had reformed himself. Since the letter did not evoke a favourable response, the Malwa sultan marched towards Kalpi. In a series of battles, Malwa had the upper hand. Realizing his military weakness, Sultan Maḥmūd Sharqī agreed to restore Kalpi to Nāṣir Khān, and the conflict came to an end.¹⁰⁹

Subsequently, Nāṣir Khān of Kalpi became a vassal of the Sharqī sultan in order to avoid further conflict, for all his old supporters had already accepted allegiance to the latter. Since then Kalpi became a part of the Sharqī sultanate. In the year 1479, Sultan Bahlūl Lodī, having driven away Sultan Ḥusayn Sharqī from Jaunpur, occupied Kalpi along with other territories. He entrusted the charge of Kalpi to his grandson, A'zam Humāyūn Lodī. During the Lodi regime, none of the scions of the Kalpi dynasty, except the Jathra branch, appears to have held any important position. Khān-i A'zam Tātār Khān, son of Masnad-i 'Āli Ismā'il Khān of Jathra is mentioned in the list of the nobles of Sultan Sikandar Lodī (1489-1517).¹¹⁰ Tātār Khān's son, Muḥammad Khān of Jathra, was one of the nobles of both Sultan Ibrāhīm Lodī and Bābur. His son, Bāyazīd Khān of Jathra, was favoured by Humāyūn with precious gifts in 1533.¹¹¹ According to Shaykh Rizq Allāh Mushtāqī, no Mughal noble could rival Muḥammad Khān

(108) *Ibid.*, pp. 59-60; also Firishtah, pp. 247-48.

(109) Nizām al-Dīn Aḥmad, *Ṭabaqāt-i Akbarī*, ed. B. Day, vol. i (Calcutta, 1927), 315.

(110) *Ṭabaqāt-i Akbarī*, vol. i, p. 315.

(111) Khwāndamīr, *Qānān-i Humāyūnī*, ed. M. Hidayat Husain (Calcutta, 1940), p. 98.

of Jathra in culture and sophistication.¹¹² This points to the fact that Jathra continued to flourish as a centre of culture and learning till the first half of the 16th century.

During the Lodi period, the territory of Kalpi was held by one of the Lodi princes. The city continued to flourish and successive *muqta's* were known for their extravagance and generous patronage of scholars and artists. One of the princes, Jalāl Khān Lodī, known as Jighat, was one of those who loved pomp and show. Besides other aristocratic paraphernalia, he had a large number of women, including dancing girls, whose maintenance involved huge expenditure. Hundreds of rupees were spent on buying flowers for the harem.¹¹³ Building activities also continued during this time.¹¹⁴ The revenue of Kalpi, excluding that of the *iqṭā'* of Jathra, amounted to 42,855,950 *tankahs*¹¹⁵ (a silver coin that was equivalent to a silver *rupia*, introduced by Sher Shāh later). The Lodi *muqta'* of Kalpi maintained 12,000 *sawārs* (horsemen), an equal number of footmen and many war-elephants.¹¹⁶

In conclusion it may be stressed that the dissolution of the Sultanate of Delhi at the beginning of the 15th century was paradoxically paralleled by the proliferation of Indo-Muslim culture, socio-economic growth and the emergence of new centres of Islamic learning in different regions that were ruled in the past by the Delhi sultan through governors (called *wālis* or *muqta's*). The metropolitan cities founded by the regional sultans had, like religion and philosophy, intellectual and historical dimensions. In each regional sultanate, small as well as big, socio-economic growth and increase in Muslim population resulted partly from the process of urbanization and partly

(112) *Wāqī'āt-i Mushtāqī*, f. 45a.

(113) *Ibid.*

(114) Cf. *Epigraphia Indica*, Arabic and Persian Supplement (1953-54), pp. 36-38.

(115) *Bāburnāmah*, vol. ii, p. 521.

(116) *Ṭabaqāt-i Akbarī*, vol. i, p. 329; Ni'mat Allāh, *Tārīkh-i Khān-i Jahānī*, vol. i (Dacca), p. 203; *Mir'āt-i Sikandarī*, pp. 288-89.

because of the Muslim socio-political system. The social role of the Sufis in particular and of the ruling elite in general was largely positive. At least in the lives and practices of genuine Sufis and representative 'Ulamā', Islamic concepts of egalitarianism and universal brotherhood found expression. Also the contribution made by these men to the progress and growth of Indo-Persian literature was great. Some of the best Persian *ghazals* were composed and sung in the *khānqāhs* of Sufis. Further, it may be pointed out that for a proper study of the history and culture of the Mughal Empire, it is imperative to study in depth the social and economic developments in the regional sultanates during the 15th century; indeed the basic material for the social life and culture of the Mughal Empire was prepared there.

BOOK REVIEWS

ERIC L. ORMSBY

THEODICY IN ISLAMIC THOUGHT

Princeton University Press, New Jersey, 1984; 309 pp.

Theodicy so far as its name goes is made familiar to us by the great German philosopher and mathematician Leibniz (A.D. 1646-1716), who wrote a book of the same name in French. But the problem is not new to Islamic theologians and thinkers. They discussed the issue with as much fervour as their counterparts in the West. Theodicy involves the question of the presence of evil in the world in spite of God's benevolence and goodness. What kind of world is this in which we live? Both Leibniz and al-Ghazālī (A.D. 1058-1111) long before him thought that it was "the Best of all possible worlds" If we say that the world is best of all possible worlds, why then is there so much suffering and evil? Why did not God create a better world, if He is omnipotent? If He could create it but did not, does it not mean that He is not benevolent enough? We are not concerned here with the way in which Leibniz tried to escape from the dilemma through his classification of different categories of evil which, according to him, are three in kind, the physical, the moral and the metaphysical. The metaphysical evil is man's finitude on which ultimately all other evils are based. We cannot of course ask why man is finite. In Islamic thought it was al-Ghazālī who raised this problem and many thinkers who succeeded him had to

reckon with him in their speculation no matter whether they agreed with him or differed violently. The whole problem, be it in Western or in Islamic thought, envisages two conflicting views on the nature of the universe: the optimistic view which sees in God's creation nothing but perfection, and the pessimistic view which considers it the worst of all possible worlds. In the history of Islamic thought the pessimistic view could not gain ground as it is determined by religious perception.

Mr. Eric L. Ormsby, Director of Libraries at the Catholic University of America, has presented us with a scholarly study of the whole problem in the context of Islamic thought. It is both a historical survey and analytical clarification of the problem. It was al-Ghazālī's one sentence statement that there is "no possibility of anything more wonderful than what is" which provoked interminable controversy.

As the writer points out, al-Ghazālī's aim was not only theoretical but also practical, and that was to produce trust (*tawakkul*) in man. This was equally the aim of another eminent Sufi Abū Ṭālib al-Makkī from whom al-Ghazālī drew inspiration. It is the emphasis on the Perfect Rightness of the things as they are which can produce in man

sorely an onleading, annotated bibliography which should include primary sources in English or English translation — offer themselves to the student

intent upon entering a critical pondering of the grave and decisive question which continue to mark the South Asian Sub-continent to this day.

(CHRISTIAN W. TROLL

A. RAHMAN, M. A. ALVI, S. A. KHAN GHORI
AND K. V. SAMBA MURTHY

*SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY IN MEDIEVAL INDIA—
A BIBLIOGRAPHY OF SOURCE MATERIALS
IN SANSKRIT, ARABIC AND PERSIAN*

Indian National Science Academy, New Delhi, 1982;
xxxi+719 pp.; price Rs. 200/- or \$ 70/-.

This book is a very valuable compendium of the source material in Arabic, Persian and Sanskrit languages of science and technology in medieval India. It begins with a Foreword by Professor M.G. K. Menon and an Introduction by Professor A. Rahman. The source material has been presented under the following heads: medicine, astronomy, mathematics, alchemy, physics, agriculture, botany, zoology, geography, gemology, architecture, encyclopaedia and dictionary.

This bibliography highlights the intellectual endeavours of the scientists in Asia in medieval times and the standards attained by them. As stated by Professor Menon in his Foreword, "a history of science and technology which is truly international, and covers objectively the contributions of different geographical

areas, has yet to be written." The present work would be exceedingly helpful to research scholars in history of science striving for this laudable aim. It would also be of much interest to scientists who would like to know the contributions of their predecessors in their areas of science.

The Arabs made a profound impact on the development of scientific thought in the world. The author has rightly commented: "Despite our debt to European Renaissance, modern science owes its birth to the Arabs." The following quotation from our earlier Prime Minister, Jawaharlal Nehru, supports this view and also sheds light on the close interaction between the Arabs and Indians in the past:

Among the ancients we do not find the scientific method in Egypt or

China or India. We find just a bit in old Greece. In Rome again it was absent. But the Arabs had this scientific method of inquiry, and so they may be considered as fathers of modern science. In some subjects like medicine and mathematics they learnt much from India. Indian scholars and mathematicians came in large numbers to Baghdad. Many Arab scientists went to Takshashila in North India, which was still a great university specializing in Medicine. Sanskrit books on medical and other subjects were especially translated into Arabic. Many things—for example, paper making—the Arabs learnt from China. But on the basis of knowledge gained from others they made their own researches and made several important discoveries. They made the first telescope and mariner's compass. In medicine, Arab physicians were famous all over Europe. (Jawaharlal Nehru, *Glimpses of World History* [Asia Publishing House, 2nd edition], p. 155.)

With regard to the development of astronomy, Pannekoek wrote that the Arabs considerably influenced the first rise of astronomy in medieval Europe. (A. Pannekoek, *A History of Astronomy* [Interscience, New York, 1961].)

It is worthy of note that the Holy

Qur'an provides considerable motivation for the study of science, and the Prophet Muhammad, may peace and blessings of God be on him, laid great stress on acquisition of knowledge. The Arabs had followed the instructions of their master.

A broad picture of the subjects and the nature of the manuscripts is provided by tables which give an analysis of the output of documents according to subjects, language and century. A large number of manuscripts could not be dated. It can be readily seen that scientific activity was continuous throughout the Medieval Ages. Although the areas of study covered a wide range of subjects, the greatest activity was in medicine, astronomy and mathematics. The number of manuscripts in Arabic and Persian are comparable to those in Sanskrit. A close study may disclose several interesting interactions, for example, the work of Raja Sewai Jai Singh II reflects such an interaction in astronomy.

It is obvious that tremendous painstaking efforts have been put into the preparation of this bibliography. May Almighty God bless this work bountifully.

SALEH MOHAMMED ALLADIN